

ABSTRACT

Long noncoding RNA (lncRNA) profile expression for the identification of novel ceRNAs associated with chemoresistance to Gemcitabine in Pancreatic Ductal Adenocarcinoma

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Pancreatic cancer is a highly aggressive disease, harvesting thousands of lives annually around the globe. The most frequent form is the pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) that affects the exocrine portion of the organ, which is characterized by high levels of mortality. In the last decade, large scale gene expression profiling studies revealed that the majority of the cellular transcriptional output is composed of non-coding RNAs (ncRNAs), which may act in gene expression regulation and contribute to the establishment of cellular phenotypes. With respect to such complexity, a broader knowledge regarding gene expression regulation mechanisms driven by ncRNAs may contribute to the comprehension of the molecular biology of PDAC and, thus, lead to the identification of novel targets for treatment. In 2011, the hypothesis that different classes of cellular RNAs, whether coding for proteins or not, could act as competing endogenous RNAs (ceRNAs), was proposed. Accordingly, ceRNAs are RNAs that possess regions of interaction with microRNAs and thus could act as competitors, preventing specific microRNAs from targeting their primary mRNA targets, thereby providing an additional layer of gene expression regulation. In this sense, this ongoing project aims to identify and characterize ceRNA regulatory gene networks comprising microRNAs, lncRNAs and mRNAs that contribute to chemoresistance in PDAC. A dataset comprising global gene expression of RNA-Seq data from 28 samples of patient-derived PDAC xenografts (PDXs) treated with the drug gemcitabine, the primary chemotherapeutic strategy for PDAC was used. The ceRNA-lncRNA identification comprised the evaluation of RNA-Seq data gene expression profile. For that, the analysis strategy involved extracting raw data from the Sequence Read Archive (SRA) platform, mapping trimmed reads against the human genome (GRCh38) using the STAR software, quantifying these reads with featureCounts, and performing differential expression analysis using the DESeq2 package. The GTF file was used for the characterization of RNA classes and differential expression analysis of lncRNAs. Analysis of miRNA-Seq data from these 28 PDXs samples using a Perl script (shortCat), previously built by our group, are yet to be performed. A global network of ceRNA will be built using RNA-Seq and miRNA-Seq count matrices and a list of lncRNA-miRNA-mRNA interactions as input. For that, the software SPONGE will be used. The list of differentially expressed lncRNAs genes will be used to identify ceRNA-lncRNA genes from the global network of ceRNA. Considering a threshold of $\log_2\text{FoldChange} \geq |0.5|$ with an adjusted pvalue ≤ 0.05 , a total of 1,468 lncRNAs (1,385 upregulated and 83 downregulated) were detected as differentially expressed in resistance samples, compared to sensitive controls. The set of gemcitabine-responsive lncRNAs will be used in downstream analyses to identify lncRNAs that may contribute to chemoresistance by acting as ceRNAs.

Keywords: lncRNAs; ceRNAs; Transcriptomics; RNA-Seq; Cancer; PDAC.

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